

Reconnecting protected areas in working landscapes

ALIGNING ECOLOGICAL POTENTIAL WITH SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

Contributors:

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 Reconnect

Current global biodiversity strategies, such as the Kunming-Montreal Framework and the EU Nature Restoration Regulation, emphasize the need to look beyond protected areas. To halt biodiversity loss, conservation must be integrated into the wider “working landscapes”: the agricultural, forestry, and urban areas that surround nature reserves, as well as marine and coastal production zones. However, implementing this integration faces significant challenges: ecological models do not always align with social acceptance, and the benefits of nature are not always distributed equally. While this brief focuses on terrestrial systems, the presented principles of alignment between ecological potential and social feasibility are equally relevant for aquatic and offshore environments.

The **Grenoble region** (French Alps) offers a high-contrast interface between mountains, cities, and farmland. Based on this exemplar region, this brief offers evidence-based guidance for reconnecting landscapes in a way that is both ecologically effective and socially feasible.

Key messages:

- **Protected area borders do not function as rigid ecological barriers:** While administrative boundaries are clearly defined, their impact on the surrounding landscape varies significantly. Some borders show a sharp decline in ecosystem services immediately outside the protected area, whereas others act as porous transitions where protected and unprotected areas together reinforce landscape multifunctionality.
- **Different spatial configurations come with trade-offs:** There is no single optimal landscape. Restoring large, connected habitats benefits particular biodiversity elements and ecosystem services such as recreation, while dispersed natural elements, like hedgerows, better support pollination and climate adaptation in productive lands.
- **Technical diagnosis guides participation:** Purely technical restoration plans are ecologically efficient but often socially difficult to implement. Using technical data to inform, rather than dictate, participatory processes can achieve high impact with lower social conflict.
- **Equity should be a priority:** In urban areas, for example, a mismatch often exists between where nature provides climate regulation (e.g., cooling) and where vulnerable populations live. Green planning must prioritize these high-challenge areas and connect them with high natural value landscapes such as protected areas.

Shared challenges and policy implications

1. Diagnosing the interface: beyond administrative boundaries

Protected areas are often managed as islands, but their ability to provide ecosystem services, and the ability of the surrounding landscape to sustain them, depends on the ecological connectivity across their borders. Our analysis of ecosystem services reveals that these interfaces function in diverse ways.

While a sharp decline in ecosystem service provision outside protected areas is common in intensive agricultural and urban zones, it is not the only pattern. We identified cases where ecosystem services actually increase at the interface (see Box 1). This occurs when the surrounding landscape maintains high habitat quality, allowing for a “spillover” of benefits, for example, pest control agents finding suitable habitat patches within the agricultural or urban matrix. In these areas, rural, cultural, and urban priorities often align, creating opportunities for shared management. Recognizing this diversity is crucial; a one-size-fits-all strategy is inefficient.

Policy implication:

Spatial planning can use cross-border analyses to target interventions. Actions are needed to restore the flow of ecosystem services from the protected area to its surroundings, while areas where multiple priorities align can serve as model “living labs for coexistence”.

Box 1: Coexistence across borders

The flow of ecosystem services depends on the connectivity between protected areas, working lands, and urban landscapes.

- **Flow of organisms:** When habitat quality is maintained outside protected areas, species such as pollinators and natural pest controllers (e.g., insectivorous birds or birds of prey) can move across the landscape. This creates a “spillover effect” that supports agricultural yields and urban people’s health (e.g., mosquito control), preventing a “sharp decline” in benefits at the border.
- **Flow of people:** Connectivity also facilitates human movement, allowing people to access landscapes for outdoor recreation, which strengthens the cultural link between urban populations and nature.
- **Living labs:** While most borders trade-offs between ecosystem services linked to different management priorities, such as rural, urban, or cultural values, those specific areas where these different values and management priorities align can serve as “living labs”. These zones demonstrate that landscape multifunctionality is both ecologically and socially achievable.

2. Managing spatial trade-offs: one landscape cannot do it all

Restoring connectivity requires decisions about where and how to place natural elements. Our models show that the spatial configuration of restored areas, as large, aggregated patches or as small, dispersed elements, creates unavoidable trade-offs.

While attempting to maximize all ecosystem services simultaneously is unrealistic at the local site level, a strategic balance can be achieved at the landscape scale. Large, aggregated natural habitats strongly benefit emblematic wildlife, forest specialists, and landscape recreational value. Conversely, dispersing small natural elements (like hedgerows or riparian strips) throughout agricultural land is more effective for ecosystem services supporting food production like pollination and pest control, as well as for climate adaptation.

Policy implication:

Restoration policies, and specifically the National Restoration Plans required by the European Union Nature Restoration Regulation, need to be informed by the specific ecological and social context on the ground. Rather than a uniform approach, a shared strategic vision at the landscape scale is needed to define which spatial configuration is prioritized in each area. To meet targets effectively, policy instruments must encourage a mix of configurations: large habitat patches for species conservation, small and dispersed natural elements within agricultural matrixes to ensure functional connectivity, and green spaces in urban ecosystems that are specifically adapted to the local ecology. This balanced approach ensures that restoration supports both biodiversity and the essential functions of the working landscape.

3. Bridging the gap: technical potential vs. social feasibility

There is often a disconnect between where restoration should happen according to ecological models and where it can happen given social realities. We compared a “Technical” scenario, prioritizing restoration where ecosystem services decrease outside protected areas, with a “Participatory” scenario co-designed with stakeholders.

Our findings suggest that technical diagnoses are essential to guide stakeholder discussions through landscape transformation by revealing pathways, such as agroforestry, that might otherwise be overlooked. However, the participatory process is what allows these pathways to become feasible and co-constructed. In our study, the marginal ecological gain of the purely technical approach did not always justify the risk of high social conflict. When technical and participatory outcomes are comparable, the inclusion of local knowledge and stakeholder support adds significant value and ensures the long term success of restoration.

Policy implication:

Technical diagnoses need to be used as a tool to guide stakeholder discussions through landscape transformation rather than as a rigid blueprint. They can reveal new possibilities for the landscape, but the final restoration strategies need to be co-constructed through participatory processes to ensure they are both ecologically effective and socially feasible. In cases where high impact interventions are necessary but likely to cause conflict, policies are required to provide the specific economic and sectoral support for bridging the gap between technical potential and social acceptance.

4. Prioritizing equity across the matrix: addressing mismatches in supply and demand

The “working landscape” is not just a biophysical space; it is where people live and rely on nature. Our analysis reveals that looking solely at ecological indicators can hide significant social disparities within territories. These disparities refer to the mismatch between the supply of ecosystem services and the actual needs of vulnerable populations.

In urban and peri-urban areas, we found a critical mismatch: the most vulnerable populations (such as low-income households) often reside in areas with the lowest provision of climate-regulating services, like heat mitigation. Conversely, in rural areas, restoration plans can inadvertently place a disproportionate burden on specific groups, particularly farmers, who are often expected to implement changes without adequate support.

Policy reflection:

Equity must be a core principle for prioritization rather than an afterthought. Spatial planning needs to map hotspots where high social vulnerability overlaps with low ecosystem service provision or a high implementation burden. Furthermore, because current policy instruments and subsidies are often skewed towards purely economic outcomes, they must be redirected to prioritize social and ecological resilience. Restoration investments need to be targeted to bridge these gaps, ensuring that the benefits reach those who need them most, while the costs of implementation are fairly supported through reformed financial mechanisms.

Recommendations

To effectively reconnect people and landscapes, policymakers and practitioners need to:

- **Adopt a diagnostic approach to protected area borders:** Move from managing rigid administrative lines to managing across borders. This requires recognizing gradients of ecosystem services that both flow into and out of protected areas, and identifying where ecosystem services drop off sharply to target those specific zones for restoration.
- **Diversify restoration strategies:** Acknowledge that different landscape configurations serve different goals. National and regional planning need to translate targets, such as those in the European Union Nature Restoration Regulation, into a shared strategic vision that maintains a balance between large habitat patches for species conservation and dispersed elements within working lands.
- **Harmonize sectoral policies:** Use the EU Nature Restoration Regulation as a mechanism to align conflicting incentives. Ensure that agricultural and forestry funding supports the specific connectivity elements (e.g., hedgerows, diversified forests) identified as technically important but that can be socially difficult.
- **Target interventions for equity:** Map the overlap between social vulnerability and ecosystem service supply. Prioritize retrofitting green infrastructure in these locations to ensure a just transition.
- **Use science to support, not dictate, dialogue:** Technical spatial models serve to identify critical connectivity gaps and pathways for ecosystem service improvement across the landscape. Integrating this data into participatory processes helps stakeholders visualize how nature provides benefits across protected areas borders and ensures that restoration efforts are targeted where they achieve the highest ecological and social impact.

RECONNECT investigates the social-ecological relationships between protected areas and the larger landscapes that they are embedded in. The project explores ecological, social, and institutional connections to understand how protected areas relate to the 'outside' world. With this systemic take, the project goes beyond the conventional approach to biodiversity conservation and contributes to better coherence in discussions and decisions about the management of landscapes.

RECONNECT is 3-year long research project (2023-2026) sponsored by Biodiversa+ and the EU, with a budget of approximately 1,4 million Euro's. It spans across four different case studies, namely Stockholm (Sweden), Göttingen (Germany), Grenoble (France), and Cape Town (South Africa). The partners are: Stockholm University, IUCN European Regional Office, French National Centre for Scientific Research, University of Helsinki, University of Göttingen, University of Western Cape and University of Cape Town.

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